

Eligibility Criteria: Collaborative Lesson Development Training (CLDT) Call

Building digital skills training and lesson development capacity in the Netherlands NES domain (DC4NES) Project | 2026

About the DC4NES project

The DC4NES (Digital Capacity for Natural and Engineering Sciences) project builds digital skills training capacity in the Netherlands. It is funded by TDCC-NES and runs for two years, starting in December 2025. The project funds 3 teams of 2-3 people to join the Carpentries Collaborative Lesson Development Training (CLDT). There is a single open call, open May – July 2026. The training will take place in November 2026 in person, in the Netherlands. The time investment of the training is 16 hours, excluding preparation time.

The CLDT equips participants with the skills to develop pedagogically sound, reusable, and openly licensed lesson materials in a collaborative manner. Completed lessons are published in the Carpentries Incubator, where they are freely available to instructors worldwide. The Carpentries [website](#) provides further details for this training. The training for one team, consisting of two to three participants, is valued at approximately EUR 5,000–6,000. The training is conducted in English by Carpentries Trainers Johan Hidding and Toby Hodges.

Eligibility

Applications are submitted by teams of 2–3 people. All of the following criteria must be met.

Team composition:

- The team must consist of 2–3 people.
- At least one team member must be a certified Carpentries Instructor by the start of the training in November 2026. This is a formal requirement of The Carpentries.
- Team members from different Dutch research-performing organisations are encouraged. Teams from a single institution may apply but will be assessed against diversity criteria if the call is oversubscribed.

Proposed lesson:

- The proposed lesson must be clearly linked to the NES domain (astronomy, chemistry, computer science, earth & environmental sciences, mathematics, physics, and applied & engineering sciences).
- The proposed lesson must be feasibly teachable in a short format such as a (max) two days workshop format or another short form of training session.
- The proposed lesson must be feasibly teachable in a two-day workshop format.
- The topic should not duplicate an existing, actively maintained lesson in the Carpentries Incubator, unless the application demonstrates clear added value.
- The language of the proposed lesson must be in English or Dutch.

- Using existing local teaching material and turning it into an openly available Carpentry-style lesson is also possible.

Institutional commitment:

- The team's institution(s) must commit to hosting the full workshop of the newly developed lesson. No additional funding is provided for hosting the workshop.
- The team must agree to publish all lesson materials openly in the Carpentries Incubator under an open license.

Related documents

You can find all related documents in the Digital Capacity for NES community on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/communities/dc4nes>

- Selection Criteria: CLDT Call
- Selection Process: CLDT Call